

Triple multiplication relationship theorem

$$G \mid (R + L)$$

$$R \mid (G - L)$$

$$L \mid (G - R)$$

(where G, R, L are all natural numbers.)

The only solution that satisfies all three conditions is

$$G = R + L$$

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Proof)

It is difficult when considering the entire range of integers, but it is simple because it is range of natural numbers.

Three conditions are set as follows:

$$Gx = R + L \quad (\alpha)$$

$$Ry = G - L \quad (\beta)$$

$$Lz = G - R \quad (\gamma)$$

x, y, z are natural numbers.

Add equation (α) and equation (β)

We have three cases to consider.

i) $x=y$

$$Gx + Ry = x(R + G) = R + G$$

$$\therefore x = 1$$

ii) $x > y$, so let $x = y + x_1$

when we add,

$$Gy + Gx_1 + Ry = (G + R)y + Gx_1 = G + R$$

y is at least 1. And also x_1 is at least 1.

Therefore the left-hand side is always bigger than right-hand side.

Therefore ii) is impossible.

iii) $y > x$, so let $y = x + y_1$

If we add,

$$Gx + Rx + Ry_1 = (G + R)x + Ry_1 = G + R$$

x is at least 1. And also y_1 is at least 1.

Therefore,

$$(G + R)x + Ry_1 = G + R$$

The left-hand side is always bigger than right-hand side.

Therefore iii) is impossible.

In conclusion, only case i) is possible.

$$Gx = R + L$$

$$Ry = G - L$$

$$x = y = 1$$

$$G = R + L$$

$$R = G - L$$

(These two equations are equivalent.)